

Appendices

Appendix A: Lego Serious Play Sets

The only way the Lego company is involved with LSP is that they are the sole sellers of the LSP Lego sets. The four available LSP sets were put together specifically for LSP workshops and include the following four sets:

Window Exploration Set

This is the set that we use in most of our teaching sessions. Each bag includes enough Lego bricks for one student and when needed, educators can combine many bags together to give to teams to work together. The limited number of bricks included in this bag are enough for students to be creative and expressive but not too many that they have to spend a lot of time going through each individual piece.

Starter Kit Set

That is an intermediate set that includes more pieces than the window exploration set and can be used in longer sessions where educators are looking to give students the time and opportunity to explore the learning content in more depth.

Identity and Landscape Set

That is one of the two larger sets that should be used only in longer sessions, for example a two or three hour session where students can freely explore the learning content.

Connections Set

The second large set of LSP bricks should also be used only in longer sessions and only when the aim of the session is to make connections between different agents, ideas, theories or events that connect to the learning content that is being discussed.

Appendix B: Lesson Plan for One-hour Organisational Sustainability Seminar

Drawing from the example of sustainability as outlined in the main body of this article, the following Learning Plan aims at providing a framework for educators that want to deliver one-hour responsible management seminars using case studies on organisational sustainability with the LSP methodology. Please take note that the very first time you introduce a group of students to LSP, warm up exercises are of paramount importance for the students to understand how the LSP methodology works. Facilitating warm up exercises means that you have less time for case study related questions so the very first session might include one case study related question unlike the following Lesson Plan that includes two.

/ Lesson Plan	
Bridge-In (Motivation)	Achieve a deeper understanding of organisational sustainability issues and of the potential approaches addressing these issues
Assessment	Informal Assessment of the Analysis of the Case Study of each student/student team
Learning Objectives	Better understanding of how organisations approach sustainability issues, what the issues are and how the decisions made by organisational leaders affect the outcome of such undertakings.

/	Instructor Activities	Learner Activities	Resources	Time (Minutes)
1. Introduction to the session	State aim of session and distribute register	Sign Register	PowerPoint Slides, Register	5
2. Lego Warm Up Exercises	Explain aim of Lego and facilitate students building simple Lego models (two exercises)	Build Lego models, discuss Lego models within their teams	PowerPoint Slides, Lego Bricks	20 (10 if students are familiar with LSP, one instead of two warm up exercises)
3. Organisational Sustainability Case Study	Brief presentation of the general background of the case study	Take notes of the major sustainability challenges presented to the organisation	PowerPoint Slides	10
4. LSP Question	Introduce the first question: What are the main sustainability problems and risks that the organisation is facing? Build Lego model	Build Lego models responding to the question	Lego Bricks, Slides	5
5. LSP Sharing	Facilitate sharing of Lego models, share their own insights	Share insights built into Lego models	Lego bricks,	10 (timings during this stage of the process depend on student numbers, we would advice each student to be given a minute to present their model. In larger classrooms it is advisable for students to be organised in smaller groups.)

6. LSP Reflection	Summarise themes discussed during the sharing stage, connect them to theory	Take notes of themes		5
7. LSP Question	Introduce the second question: What are the potential solutions to these problems and risks, what should the business do to solve these issues?	Build Lego models responding to the question	Lego Bricks, Slides	5
8. LSP Sharing	Facilitate sharing of Lego models, share their own insights	Share insights built into Lego models	Lego bricks,	10 (timings during this stage of the process depend on student numbers, we would advice each student to be given a minute to present their model. In larger classrooms it is advisable for students to be organised in smaller groups.)
9. LSP Reflection	Summarise themes discussed during the sharing stage, connect them to theory	Take notes of themes		5